

GREENING INDIA FINANCIAL MARKETS

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ABSTRACT

In India, the opportunity for green” financial institutions known as green banks which can attract and channelize the international capital and increase the pace of domestic investment by leveraging limited public funds, resulting in affordable capital to scale up the clean energy. The key barriers to clean energy finance in India include lack of enough domestic debt capital to finance infrastructure, high perceived risk, lack of knowledge within the domestic banking sector and currency risks for foreign investors. This paper is to highlight the importance of green bank in India and its opportunity. Green finance correlates with the economic growth along with the international cooperation.

Key Words: Green Bank, Financial Institutions, Finance and Risk

INTRODUCTION

The most inspiring idea in modern business is Corporate Social Responsibility, even in financial business. CSR, already widely implemented in economy, consist of significant ecological components, it basically focuses on the challenge of measuring progress around mobilizing capital for 'green' investments and shifting capital out of 'brown' investments.

Every stage of business life cycle requires finance; whether it is micro, medium or large scale no difference. Global warming is forcing governments all over the world to overcome this disaster by following any programs of the United Nations like Kyoto Protocol or any other. Green finance is an essential tool to support green growth, by which environmental protection and economic development can take place. It is future oriented and motivated on green economic activities.¹

Green Finance has great role to play in green growth. It correlates financial industry environmental improvement and economic growth. Financial industry needs to develop green financial products which promote various investment opportunities in green industries and technologies. They can offer products and services to request more environmentally friendly consumers such as energy efficiency mortgages, green car loans, alternate energy venture capital, green credit cards, eco - friendly deposits etc.² Since environmental risks and opportunities are more, there can be options for reconciliation with lending and financing arrangements.³ During the present time, around the world many Financial market actors' lending and investment practices have a great impact on the real economy such as financial institution, leading banks, investment funds, pension funds, corporate, use environmental aspects in their business, and

¹. Kiyeon, *Green Financing to be Prompted*, Retrieved from <https://fsckorea.wordpress.com/tag/green-economy/>

². Miguelitodh, *Development of Green Finance and Its Implication on Korean Financial Market*, Retrieved from <https://fsckorea.wordpress.com/tag/green-mortgage/>

³. *Green Financial Products and Services, Current Trends and Future Opportunities in North America- A report of the North American Task Force (NATF) of the United Nations Environment Programme Finance Initiative, 2007, ICF Consulting Canada, Inc., Toronto, p.-9*

protect the environment and conserve natural resources are green financing tools.⁴ (*Priscilla, Kristine, Wilson, Dick 2009*)

These financial market actors' plays an important role in underpinning natural environment in many different ways like saving resources, financing pro-ecological organizations, maintaining ample Public Relation and Investor Relation communication and even offering special financial products. Substantially, the new investment possibilities are clear evidence of positive changes also of the Polish financial market which particularly emphasis on two sections of 'climate-friendly' finance. In first it focuses on what we know about 'green' finance across asset classes, with a particular emphasis on questions around high-carbon and low-carbon finance.⁵ In second, it maps the current options for benchmarking climate finance, as one aspect of the green finance space, to public policy objectives.

The transition to a net-zero emissions world and sustainable global economy, will require change across the financial sector which is based on two pillars: (i) acknowledgement and transparency of finance flows which deliver environmental benefits, and (ii) a metrics-based empowerment of financial actors championing investments in projects or companies that deliver environmental benefits and support sustainable development.

The growing and diversified ecological engagement of different financial institutions could be even termed as ecological evolution of financial business.⁶ (*Leszek, 2014*)
The new trend in financial business is apparent, whereby companies not only consider their

⁴. Priscilla.E.Hampton, Kristine, R., Wilson, Bruce E., Dick, & Mark, D., Whitlow, 2009, *Green Financing: Tax Incentives and Financing Programs Supporting Green Building*, Retrieved from <http://www.mondaq.com/unitedstates/x/80794/Energy+Law/Green+Financing+Tax+Incentives+And+Financing+Programs+Supporting+Green+Building>

⁵. https://www.bafu.admin.ch/dam/bafu/fr/dokumente/klima/externe-studien/berichte/measuring_progressongreeningfinancialmarkets.pdf.download.pdf/measuring_progressongreeningfinancialmarkets.pdf

⁶. Leszek Dziawgo, 2014, *Greening Financial Market*, *Copernican Journal of Finance and Accounting*, Vol.-1, Issue-3, pp.-9-24

profitability and growth, but also the interests of the society.⁷ The environment by taking responsibility for the impact of their activities on stakeholders, environment, consumers, employees, communities and all other members of the public sphere.⁸ (*Chakraborty, 2010*)

Triple Bottom Line Approach of CSR which is gaining significance and becoming popular amongst corporates is “People, Planet and Profit” which is used to succinctly describe the triple bottom line.⁹ “People” (Human capital) pertains to fair and beneficial business practices towards labor and the community and region in which a corporation conducts its business. “Planet” (Natural Capital) refers to sustainable environmental practices.¹⁰ It is the lasting economic impact the organization has on its economic environment. A TBL company endeavors to benefit the natural order much as possible or at the least do no harm and curtails environment impact. “Profit” is the bottom line shared by all commerce.¹¹

GREEN FINANCE YEAR

In 2016, G20 heads of state for the first time recognized the need to ‘scale up green finance’ setting out a series of steps to make this happen. Leading insurance regulators also decided to work together on how to respond to sustainability challenges, such as climate change. In all, UN Environment estimates that the number of policy measures to green the financial system has more than doubled to over 200 measures across 60 countries.

⁷. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Sudeepta_Pradhan/publication/233262018_CSR_and_Performance_The_Story_of_Banks_in_India/links/566a9c1d08aea0892c4a1e0c.pdf

⁸. Chakraborty, Saheli, 2010, *Corporate Social Responsibility and The Society, Business That Cares- Innovative Ideas For Profit, Purpose, and People*, Retrieved from <http://businessthatcares.blogspot.in/2010/08/corporate-social-responsibility-and.html>

⁹. *Ethics, Governance and Sustainability, 2014, The Institute of Company Secretaries of India, Delhi Computer Services, Dwarka, New Delhi*

¹⁰. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Triple_bottom_line

¹¹. Siddharth Academy, *Corporate Social Responsibility*, Retrieved from <http://siddharthacademy.in/images/Downloads/Company%20Secretary%20Free%20Notes/CS%20PROFESSIONAL/Ethics-Gov-and-Sustainability.pdf>

Importantly, these policy are closely connected with the rapid growth of green finance in the marketplace. With global carbon emissions stalling and clean tech costs plummeting, the task ahead for green finance in 2017 is to step up the pace. Financial institutions with assets worth tens of trillions of dollars are now committed to aligning their portfolios with the low-carbon transition and sustainable development more broadly. Yet the actual reallocation of capital still remains insufficient.

ROADMAPS FOR GREEN AND SUSTAINABLE FINANCE

One of the key insights from the G20's work on green finance on 2016 was that governments need to be work upon the policy signals they send to financiers about their plans for climate action. What is key to these roadmaps is making the bridge between high-level national targets and the technical details of how money actually flows across banking, insurance and investment.

INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION ON RULES OF THE GAME

Central banks, finance ministries and regulators are starting to make sustainability factors a routine part of financial practice through measures to build competence and strengthen accountability. The international cooperation is important to share emerging experience and ensure that there is a convergence on key rules of the game .The striking part about the breakthroughs made in 2016 was how countries observed what others were doing - and then put in place measures to boost national action that were allied with international best practices.

Insurance is another key area where both financial institutions and financial regulators are moving ahead with common approaches. Closing the growing protection gap between the economic and insured losses from natural hazards is a growing concern, a gap that will be widened with climate change. Heading into 2017, the Forum will emphasis on disclosure, access to insurance, sustainable insurance roadmaps, climate risk, disaster risk reduction and capacity building for supervisors.

KEY TAKEAWAYS: BENEFITS OF A GREEN BANK IN INDIA

A green bank is an institution that is more than the sums of its parts. Green banks are a new kind of specialized intermediary designed to quicken the maturation of clean energy markets. Their role is not to replace or “crowd out” commercial banks and private investors but to “crowd in” private capital. Green banks use private-sector experience and discipline in the service of the public good and play a transformative role with their limited engagement with markets, nor can the private sector, with its competitive pressures and fiduciary constraints, reliably achieve this outcome.

A Green Bank can introduce to the market reduced lending rates and flexible terms that match the terms and payback period of clean energy projects. This enables a broader pool of clean energy projects to be viable, making the projects more likely to be developed and also attract diverse investors, including directing international sources of capital to local projects.

VALUE PROPOSITION FOR GREEN BANKS IN INDIA

Green banks can help leverage limited public finance to drive private investment to grow the domestic clean energy market, providing the many benefits specifically to India. Green banks offer solutions to overcome local financing barriers for clean energy and can play a significant role in accelerating low carbon development projects by doing the following:

- **Attract, coordinate, and deploy capital:** Research on the Indian clean energy markets suggests that instruments like government bonds, infrastructure debt funds, partial credit guarantees, partial risk guarantees and currency hedging facilities could address core limitations of Indian debt markets. Staffed with finance professionals and capitalized with low cost funds, an Indian green bank would be a nexus for the development and deployment of such products. The green banks would serve as a bridge between government ministries and private markets to ensure market responsiveness in the service of the public interest. The green bank would be endowed with sufficient flexibility to

evolve products in real time as information on their performance comes in. {Climate Policy Initiative}

- **Reduce perceived financing risk:** High financing risk is commonly expressed by traditional bankers in India, unfamiliar with clean energy technologies as a reason for higher cost financing. Green banks can offer products such as partial credit guarantees, insurance, or loan-loss reserves that reduce the risk and therefore the cost of capital.

INDIAN RENEWABLE ENERGY DEVELOPMENT AGENCY (IREDA) AND NATIONAL CLEAN ENVIRONMENT FUND (NCEF)

IREDA was established on March 11, 1987 as a Public Limited Government Company under the Companies Act of 1956 with the goal to “promote, develop and extend financial assistance for Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency/Conservation Projects.” IREDA has been notified as a “Public Financial Institution” under section 4 ‘A’ of the Companies Act, 1956 and registered as a Non-Banking Financial Company (NFBC) with the Reserve Bank of India (RBI). The main objectives of IREDA include giving financial support to specific projects for generating electricity and energy through new and renewable sources and conserving energy through energy efficiency. IREDA’s mission is “Be a pioneering, participant friendly and competitive institution for financing and promoting self-sustaining investment in energy generation from Renewable Sources, Energy Efficiency and Environmental Technologies for sustainable development.”

One of IREDA’s important functions is providing low interest bearing funds and refinance schemes to viable renewable energy projects based on capital from the National Clean Environment Fund (NCEF). NCEF was established by the Government of India by levying a cess (tax) on coal produced in India as well as from imported coal. The IREDA NCEF Refinance Scheme aims to bring down the cost of funds for renewable energy projects by providing refinance at concessional rates of interest, with funds sourced from the NCEF. {Policy Perspectives: Green Investment Banks}

CONCLUSION

The predominant financial instruments in green finance are debt and equity. Financial instruments have several features, such as level of seniority (junior equity versus preferred stock), the channel through which the flow of finance is arranged and the intermediary actors (types of investors and investment vehicles), terms of the agreement and origin of funds among others. This brochure focuses on those related to debt and equity, as well as risk management product - a guarantee Equity financing, often used in the early stages of developing a project or company, is the method of investing capital in a company stock in return for an ownership interest. Equity, also called stock or shares, can be split into preferred stock and common stock. There are two major distinctions between the types of shares. If a company must liquidate and pay all creditors and bondholders, preferred shareholders are paid first. If any money is left, common stockholders will receive their payments. Second, the dividends of preferred stocks are different from and generally greater than those of common stock. In green finance, we often see investments in “junior equity”, which normally refers to the common stock in a company. In the event of liquidation, the company would pay out preferred stockholders before holders of junior equity.

On the other hand, holders of company bonds are paid before holders of preferred stock. The GEF invests money in junior equity to absorb some of the risk for other (private) equity investors. Essentially, when they see investments in junior equity, other equity investors are attracted to purchase preferred stock. This ensures they have first claim on distribution of profit and reduces their risk. Debt financing is typically used at later stages of development and often in combination with equity. In debt financing, investors lend money to borrowers, who pay back this amount (the principal) with interest under for more information on debt and equity instruments, their main features and use in climate financing, see UNEP (2014) Demystifying Private Climate Finance. Introduction to Green Finance 1 strict conditions. If a company liquidates its assets, debt has higher priority than, or is “senior” to, equity. In other words, a company must meet its obligations to creditors (those who lent the money) before it pays those

who borrowed money to invest in equity. As a result, more senior debt has a greater level of security, which allows for a lower interest payment than more junior security (also known as subordinated debt). Debt financing can come from a lender's loan or from selling bonds to the public. While a loan is a transfer of money from a bank to a company/individual, a bond is a transfer of money from the public/market to a company that issues a bond. Unlike loans provided through bank debt, bonds traded on public debt markets tend to involve larger amounts of capital (typically US\$100 million and above) and are open to the general public for investments. Bonds in the green finance field have been targeted more at qualified investors.

However, certain types of notes (e.g. promissory or structured notes) have also been made accessible and affordable to retail investors because they require less upfront investment. How much debt, and how much equity is right for a project or a company, varies by industry. Fast-growth fields with potential for high returns, such as software and biotech, attract equity investors more easily. Those companies also often have intangible assets and uncertain cash flow. This makes it difficult to forecast debt repayment schedules and conditions. As a result, they are often unable to borrow at workable rates.

Debt investments typically involve less risk than equity investments. Consequently, they also typically offer a lower potential return on investment. Debt and equity funds are investment vehicles of choice in environmentally related finance. This is because they enable project and cash flow to aggregate into one common investment vehicle. This vehicle combines several projects that may have a different focus, such as land use, forestry and agriculture. Whatever their focus, they have the same level of maturity (either early stage development, proven concept or mature). However, they use distinct scaling and risk mitigation strategies.

Finally, funds typically allow for risk diversification among projects/investments. Mainstream investors are usually more familiar with their structure, and thus more comfortable investing in them. Investors often manage risk using loan/credit guarantees from public finance institutions that protect them against defaults on their loans. This instrument transfers part or all of the risk from the lender onto the public institution (loan guarantor). In this way, the lender can charge a

private investor a lower interest rate on the loan, thereby lowering its cost of capital and increasing its profitability. Similar to guarantees, other risk management tools are used to leverage debt or equity investments. Public institutions can insure private investors against risks arising from policy uncertainty. Foreign exchange liquidity facilities can help reduce the risks associated with borrowing money in a different currency. They do this by creating a line of credit, which the project can draw upon when it needs money. It repays the credit when the project has a financial surplus due to currency fluctuations.

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